

Proton NMR Studies of Bioactive Compounds in Aqueous Solution^{1†}

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Techniques have been developed for using aqueous solutions of natural products directly to record 1D and 2D proton NMR spectra. Water signal suppression has been achieved without any changes in the hardware of a commercial 200 MHz NMR spectrometer. Our method requires the addition of a relaxation agent such as ammonium chloride and the use of an appropriately modified Carr-Purcell-Meiboom-Gill pulse sequence. Proton NMR spectra of water solutions of sugars and antibiotics as well as biological fluids, such as plasma, milk, urine, plant sap, fruit juices, have been studied successfully for structural and stereochemical details.

A collaborative project² on 'Bioactive Substances from the Indian Ocean' between six institutions in the United States and India was initiated in 1984. The objective of this project was basic research on Indian Ocean flora, fauna and microbes, and a search for substances having physiological activity, some of which could serve as models for new pharmaceuticals, antifouling compounds, signal substances, pheromones, etc.

One important development of potential value to the participating laboratories³ was the investigation of newer instrumental techniques that could provide detailed structural information on submilligram size samples with minimal efforts for isolation, purification and derivatization. In this context, several novel techniques of chemical ionization mass spectrometry^{4,5} were developed at Stevens for the study of mixtures isolated by thin layer chromatography (TLC).

We wish to describe here techniques that we developed for simplified approaches to proton nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy of natural products in aqueous solution. It may be noted that defense substances, sex pheromones, signal compounds and other biologically active molecules from marine species (such as algae and sponges) are originally obtained as dilute solutions in seawater. These substances are often present in the aqueous phase when conventional separation techniques are applied to complex mixtures of biological origin. Metabolites from marine microorganisms are also produced in aqueous solution during fermentation studies.

Water suppression proton NMR :

Proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy can provide valuable information regarding the structure and dynamics of biologically important molecules in solution. However, the direct analysis of organic solutes in aqueous solution, or in biological fluids such as urine, blood, plant juices, etc., by NMR spectroscopy is not possible, since the protons of water also absorb radiation in the NMR experi-

ment. In dilute aqueous samples, the molar concentration of water protons is so much higher than the concentration of solute protons that the solute resonances are inevitably swamped by the water signal.

In former years, the only recourse was to study the proton spectrum in heavy water (D₂O). This required the reconstitution of the biological fluid with D₂O, with concomitant artifact formation due to distillation, freeze-drying, recrystallization, etc. In addition, information about exchangeable protons on oxygen or nitrogen was lost.

A search through the literature showed that the water peak in proton NMR spectra of aqueous solution can be suppressed by making certain changes in the NMR spectrometer and by using specially developed computer programs. This approach involving changes both in the hardware and software was obviously expensive and not so easy to undertake when several laboratories with different types of spectrometers were in collaboration. A further search for simpler water signal suppression techniques led to the examination⁶ of a method that involves pulse sequences developed for selectively suppressing the signal due to the water resonance. The sequences avoid excitation of the water resonance, selectively saturate it, or make use of the difference in relaxation time between the water and solute protons.

In one application of the latter technique⁷, a Bronsted acid is added to the NMR solution. This significantly decreases the transverse relaxation time (T_2) of the water protons, as compared with solute protons. This difference is exploited by employing the Carr-Purcell-Meiboom-Gill⁸ pulse sequence during the T_2 relaxation period. A 90_x pulse rotates all magnetization vectors into the xy plane. After a period τ , a 180_y pulse is applied, reflecting the vectors onto the y -axis. Repeating the sequence until the vector for the water protons is a null, yields near or complete attenuation of the water resonance, while retaining the solution resonances.

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th birthday.

Experimental method

In the work reported here, this method was optimized for use with an IBM AF200 spectrometer, operating at 200 MHz proton resonance frequency with quadrature detection, and equipped with a 12 bit ADC converter and pulse programmer. The Bronsted acids used as relaxation agents (with the pH at which each was effective shown in parenthesis) were ammonium chloride (5.5–7.25), guanidinium hydrochloride (7.5–8.5) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (3.0–5.0).

Samples of biological fluids were used directly without modification, with the addition only of the relaxation agent (to a concentration of 2.5 M) and a small amount of D₂O for the deuterium lock. The spectra of sugars and other reference compounds were measured similarly, the solutions containing 0.5 mg of solute per 1.0 ml of H₂O.

Results

The feasibility of this method for various types of biological samples was studied. Low solute concentrations with complete attenuation of water resonance could be observed; thus a very satisfactory spectrum was obtained with 0.003 M solution of fructose prepared by dissolving 1 mg of the sugar in 1.8 ml of water and then adding ammonium chloride as the relaxation agent. In all cases, 1 ml of sample was pipetted into an NMR tube for analysis. Much smaller biological samples could of course be used with 400 or 500 MHz NMR spectrometers. Samples of natural products were not filtered, centrifuged or reconstituted in any form. The protons on the anomeric carbons of sugars give rise to signals at δ 4.5–5.5, well-separated from any other signals in the spectra. This method therefore appeared to be potentially very useful for natural products containing sugars or glycosides.

To test the usefulness of this 1D NMR technique, a number of sugars were analyzed to create a small database

Fig. 1a. Spectrum of glucose. Relaxation agent NH₄Cl.

Fig. 1b. Spectrum of lactose. Relaxation agent NH₄Cl.

(see for example, Fig. 1a and 1b). Then fruit juices were employed as test samples. Pear juice (Fig. 1c) showed the characteristic peaks for glucose in the 4.5–5.5 ppm region along with some other minor sugar peaks not included in our database. Fig. 1d illustrates analytical results from one brand of commercial orange juice. The water signal, which would have appeared at δ 4.2–5.5, has been completely suppressed. The resonances remaining are those of the sugars, acids and other low molecular weight organic compounds present in the juice.

Fig. 1c. Spectrum of pear juice. Relaxation agent NH₄OH/NH₂OH. HCl.

Comparison of the fruit juice spectra with the spectra of reference mono- and disaccharides made possible the qualitative and semi-quantitative estimation of the sugars present. In Fig. 1d, for example, the presence of glucose and sucrose in the orange juice is readily apparent. Similar results were also obtained with a commercial apple juice sample (Fig. 1e). It is interesting to note that sucrose is not known to be

Fig. 1d. Spectrum of orange juice. Relaxation agent $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}/\text{NH}_2\text{OH} \cdot \text{HCl}$.

a natural component of oranges or apples. This method could obviously serve as a quick procedure for testing adulteration of natural juices with 'artificial' sweeteners. This technique could also be used for comparing glycosides of natural products from related species for possible variations in the sugar moiety. Many bioactive compounds secreted into ocean water by marine organisms are known to be glycosides.

Fig. 1e. Spectrum of apple juice. Relaxation agent $\text{NH}_2\text{OH} \cdot \text{HCl}$.

The protons on the large, slowly tumbling molecules present in the biological fluids studied – the proteins and lipids – have T_2 relaxation times approaching those of water. We observed that their signals are thus almost completely absent in the water-suppressed spectra. This is advantageous for the study of the small organic compounds in these fluids, since the proteins and other larger molecules

would otherwise contribute very broad, poorly resolved peaks, which would obscure large regions of the spectrum. Therefore, it was possible to study in a simple fashion the changes in milk, which was stored at room temperature. A typical spectrum of fresh milk using ammonium chloride is shown in Fig. 2a. Lactose peaks and lipid peaks were clearly seen without any signals from proteins. After two days, peaks characteristic of lactic acid appeared (Fig. 2b).

Fig. 2a. Spectrum of milk. Relaxation agent NH_4Cl .

This method can give only semi-quantitative results since a number of variables can alter the relative signal strengths. Thus, the areas under the methylene and methyl peaks of lipids varied widely depending on the pulse sequence as is shown by the spectra of egg yolk (Fig. 3a and 3b).

Fig. 2b. Spectrum of milk after two days. Relaxation agent NH_4Cl .

Other biological samples tested were human plasma, urine and plant sap. The plasma sample (Fig. 4a) showed

Fig. 3a. Spectrum of egg yolk. Relaxation period 0.24 s.

the presence of glucose and lactic acid. The spectra of the urine sample contained some low intensity peaks for aromatic compounds. The plant sap spectrum (Fig. 4b) displayed several sugar peaks of which those due to glucose only were identified by using our very limited database.

Based on these experiments our method appears to be very convenient for studying biological fluids, natural product extracts and fermentation liquors.

Nuclear Overhauser effect :

When saturation or inversion perturbs one resonance in

Fig. 3b. Spectrum of egg yolk. Relaxation period 0.60 s.

Fig. 4a. Spectrum of human plasma. Relaxation agent NH_4Cl .

an NMR spectrum, the net intensities of some of the other resonances in the spectrum can change. This phenomenon, called the nuclear Overhauser effect (NOE or nOe), provides an indirect way for extracting information about dipolar coupling. The resonances that change their intensities are due to spins that are close in space to those directly affected by the perturbation. The nuclear Overhauser effect thus relates to internuclear interactions and hence distances between homo- and heteroatoms. The main use of NOE is for gaining information about molecular geometry.

Fig. 4b. Spectrum of plant sap. Relaxation agent NH_4Cl .

The two-dimensional (2D) experiments made possible by Fourier transform techniques have greatly extended the information on molecular structure and geometry, which can be obtained from nuclear magnetic resonance. A representative selection of useful 2D experiments are Homonuclear Correlation Spectroscopy (COSY), *J*-Resolved Spectroscopy (JRES), Heteronuclear Correlation Spectroscopy (HETCOR), Incredible Natural Abundance Double Quantum Transfer Experiment (INADEQUATE), Nuclear Overhauser Correlation Spectroscopy (NOESY).

2D-NMR with water suppression : the MODNOESY experiment :

The 2D experiment, which measures the nuclear Overhauser effect (NOESY experiment), gives information on the conformations of molecules in solution. We were interested in combining the NOESY experiment with water suppression. In this way, the conformation of molecules in aqueous solution, vital for the understanding of biological mechanisms and properties, could be determined.

In 1985 Rabenstein *et al.*¹⁰, using chemical relaxation agents and appropriate pulse sequences, were able to record COSY spectra with the attenuation of the water resonance. In 1987, Rabenstein *et al.*¹¹ used the same approach to obtain 2D *J*-resolved spectra of aqueous solutions. We were able to improve on the technique for obtaining 2D *J*-resolved spectra by modifying the pulse sequence. Satisfactory spectra were obtained for aqueous solutions of norephedrine hydrochloride⁶.

Of greater interest to us was the recording of 2D NOESY spectra in aqueous solution. The standard NOESY sequence was combined with a spin echo system that we developed. By conducting a series of experiments the pulse sequence and related parameters were optimized for complete suppression of the water resonance. A microprogram was written for a 200 MHz NMR spectrometer. This sequence, a modified NOESY program, was named MODNOESY⁶. For testing the MODNOESY sequence, experiments were performed for observing NOE enhancements in penicillin G (Fig. 5). This particular compound was selected because NOE data on it have been reported earlier using other methods. At first NOESY experiments were conducted on penicillin G sodium salt in D₂O solution. Spectra were then recorded for penicillin G sodium salt in water in presence of chemical relaxation agents (guanidine hydrochloride-NH₄Cl). By using the MODNOESY sequence it was possible to achieve complete attenuation of the resonance due to water.

Fig. 5. Penicillin G, potassium salt.

Stereochemical information :

Single crystal X-ray diffraction studies by various laboratories have shown that the amide side-chain at the 6 β -position of penicillin G can be folded over the bicyclic nucleus or be extended away from it. Also the thiazolidine ring fused to a β -lactam ring that is almost flat, can be in

two different 'envelope' conformations : in one of these conformations ('carboxy-axial') the carboxy group at C-3 and the 2 β -methyl group are nearly axial in conformation while the 3 β -H and the 2 α -methyl group are in the pseudo-equatorial position.

In penicillin G sulfoxide the thiazolidine ring assumes the 'carboxy-equatorial' conformation that places the carboxy group and the 2 β -methyl group in the pseudo-equatorial conformation – thus placing the 3 β -H and the 3 α -methyl group in the pseudo-axial position. It may be noted that in ampicillin and some other penicillins the normal conformation corresponds to the carboxy-equatorial geometry. In both conformations of the thiazolidine ring, 3 β -H is close enough to the 2 β -methyl group to experience substantial NOE¹². Molecular models indicate that in the carboxy equatorial conformation, the 2 α -methyl group would exert NOE on the 5 α -H but in the carboxy-axial conformation the 2 α -methyl group is too far away for interaction with the 5 α -H proton¹². The conformation of the side-chain and the envelope conformation of the thiazolidine ring are variable; the four-membered β -lactam ring is of fixed, nearly planar geometry. Dexter and van der Veen¹³ established that the crystalline potassium salt of penicillin G exists in the carboxy-axial/'folded side-chain' conformation. In contrast, the crystalline procaine penicillin G salt assumes the carboxy-equatorial/'extended side-chain' conformation¹³.

Proton NMR studies on penicillin esters in CDCl₃ solution have shown that substantial NOE interaction can be observed and the conformation of penicillins can be derived with confidence¹². In most cases the X-ray data are in accord with the molecular geometry predicted on the basis of NOE studies in CDCl₃ or benzene solution.

Fig. 6a. NOESY spectrum of penicillin G in D₂O.

Fig. 6b. Spectrum of penicillin G in the presence of relaxation agents using the sequence MODNOESY.

MODNOESY observations on penicillin G :

We measured the nuclear Overhauser effect in penicillin G by the conventional NOESY sequence in D_2O (Fig. 6a), and also by the MODNOESY sequence in H_2O using guanidinium chloride as the relaxation agent (Fig. 6b). In both cases, interaction was seen between 5α -H and the 2α -methyl group, across the lower face of the bicyclic nucleus, and between 3β -H and the 2β -methyl group, across the upper face. Also evident in both spectra was interaction between 3β -H and the benzyl protons, and interaction between the 2β -methyl group and the benzyl protons; these interactions confirm the existence of the folded side-chain conformation in aqueous solution, bringing the benzyl side-chain into proximity with the β -face of the bicyclic nucleus.

Of greatest interest, however, was an additional interaction in the MODNOESY/ H_2O spectrum between the benzyl protons and the α -methyl group, absent in the NOESY/ D_2O spectrum. We interpret this interaction as indicative of the carboxy-axial conformation (Fig. 7b), since only in this conformation can the benzyl group approach both methyl groups; in the carboxy-equatorial conformation (Fig. 7a) the benzyl group and the 2α -methyl group are on opposite

Fig. 7a. 'Carboxy-equatorial' conformation with folded side-chain.

sides of the molecule. Evidently, penicillin G has as its predominant conformation in aqueous solution the same carboxy-equatorial conformation that is found in the solid state for procaine penicillin. In the solution used in obtaining the MODNOESY spectrum, ion-pairing between the guanidinium ion added as the relaxation agent and the carboxylate ion at C-3 alters the steric requirements of the C-3 substituent, so that the carboxy-axial conformation (Fig. 7b) becomes the preferred one.

Fig. 7b. 'Carboxy-axial' conformation with folded side-chain.

The presence of NOE interaction between the 2α -methyl group and the 5α -H in both NOESY and MODNOESY spectra seems to indicate that an equilibrium exists between the two envelope conformations for the thiazolidine ring.

Concluding remarks :

The techniques that we have developed are applicable to any proton NMR spectrometer since no hardware changes are needed. The pulse sequences that are required for 1D proton NMR and 2D NOESY studies can be modeled after those developed by us. The relaxing agents, ammonium chloride, guanidinium chloride and hydroxylamine hydrochloride are chemically compatible with most aqueous solutions of natural products. Of particular importance is the observation that water signal suppression by this technique also suppresses almost completely the signals of proteins, lipids and other large molecules in solution. The spectra of the small organic molecules of interest are thus revealed without the need for undertaking their physical separation. Using the newer NMR instruments operating at higher frequencies it would be possible to conduct spectral examination with much smaller size samples, but with much higher resolution. This water peak suppression approach could greatly simplify some of the work of natural product chemists, microbiologists and biological chemists.

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References

1. For a related previous publication, see : H. S. GARG, M. SHARMA, D. S. BHAKUNI, B. N. PRAMANIK and A. K. BOSE. *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1992, **33**, 1641.
2. This project was jointly sponsored by the Oceanic Biology Program of the Office of Naval Research (ONR) of the United States Government and the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) and the Department of Science and Technology (DST) of the Government of India – under the authority of U. S. Public Law 480 which in part supported research of international importance to be conducted in a foreign nation (India) where an excess of U.S. currency existed.
3. The Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, was the lead institution in India with its Director serving as the chief coordinator on the Indian side. The National Institute of Oceanography, Goa and the Bose Institute, Calcutta, were the other Indian laboratories that participated. On the American side, Prof. Ajay K. Bose of Stevens Institute of Technology served as the Principal investigator. Prof. Gerald Bakus of the University of Southern California and Dr. George Ruggieri of the Osborn laboratories of Marine Sciences in New York, were the other American participants. Dr. Bernard Zahuranec represented ONR.
4. K. TABELI, M.S. Thesis, Stevens Institute of Technology, 1982. Novel technique described included TLC-CIMS, combined with TLC-O₃-CIMS, two-dimensional TLC combined with TLC-O₃-CIMS and a very soft ionization technique, termed GEL-O-CIMS, that involved covering the tip of a solid probe for CIMS with a spot of jello that was dusted with microgram quantities of sample and NH₄Cl for providing both positive and negative ion CIMS data.
5. S. SHEFER, G. SALEN, F. W. CHENG, B. DAYAL, A. K. BATTI, G. S. TINT, A. K. BOSE and B. N. PRAMANIK, *Anal. Biochem.*, 1982, **121**, 23.
6. A. KRISHNASWAMI, Ph.D. Thesis, Stevens Institute of Technology, 1991.
7. D. L. TABENSTEIN and S. FAN, *Anal. Chem.*, 1986, **58**, 3178.
8. (a) S. MEIBÖOM and D. GILL, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.*, 1958, **29**, 688; H. Y. CARR and E. M. PURCELL, *Phys. Rev.*, 1954, **94**, 530.
9. For a detailed discussion, see, for example, "The Nuclear Overhauser Effect in Structural and Conformational Analysis", D. Neuhaus and M. P. Williamson, VCH, New York, 1989.
10. D. L. RABENSTEIN, S. FAN and T. T. NAKASHIMA, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1985, **64**, 541.
11. D. L. RABENSTEIN, G. S. SRIVATSA and R. W. K. LEE, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1987, **71**, 175.
12. R. D. G. COOPER, P. V. DEMARCO, J. C. CHENG and N. D. JONES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 1408.
13. D. D. DEXTER and J. M. VAN DER VEEN, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1978, 185.